

Thirty Writers Talk about Writing

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The Signal Approach to Children's Books, edited by Nancy Chambers. Metuchen, NJ, and London: Scarecrow Press; and Harmondsworth, Middlesex: Kestrel Books, 1980.

The Openhearted Audience: Ten Authors Talk about Writing for Children, edited by Virginia Haviland. Washington: Library of Congress, 1980.

Celebrating Children's Books: Essays on Children's Literature in Honor of Zena Sutherland, edited by Betsy Hearne and Marilyn Kaye. New York: Lothrop, Lee & Shepherd, 1981.

Writers can be their own worst readers. They can tell us what they intended, but their finished work might not fulfill their intentions. Their secret reservoirs of private associations with the words they write are just as likely to mislead them as they read those words as ours might mislead me and you; and their secret knowledge of how the words they eventually chose came to be chosen might actually confuse them. Jill Paton Walsh's discussion of how she writes in *The Openhearted Audience* suggests one version of the problem: "Whereas the reader and the critic are confronted simply with the way the author did go, the author himself was confronted with an immensely elaborate network of interrelated choices. No one but a writer ever looks at a literary problem in quite this way." I doubt that anyone can ever look at a finished book in quite the way its writer does.

In adult literature, the recognition that writers are biased readers of their own words has led to a sensible division of labor. Those who can write literature, write literature; and, we hope, those who can read literature well become readers and writers about reading—that is, ^{literary} ~~literally~~ critics. When it comes to children's literature, unfortunately, that division is not so firmly made. Editors and organizers of conferences and lectures often ask children's writers to discuss their own work; and what they have to say about it often takes the

place of criticism by more objective readers. In the three books in question, there are twenty-five pieces about writing by writers and illustrators of children's books—thirty, if you count the nonfiction writers.

The presence of writers in *The Openhearted Audience* is not surprising, since the book's subtitle quite fairly announces its contents—"Ten Authors Talk about Writing for Children"—and like the British magazine its contents have been chosen from, *The Signal Approach to Children's Books* contains essays by professional critics as well as authors. *Celebrating Children's Books* is a different matter; in addition to selections by fourteen writers and illustrators, and other pieces by a mixed bag of librarians, editors, and publicists, it contains a short section called "Understanding the Books," in which the difficult art of writing about reading is represented by a grand total of two essays, both by reviewers.

Now reviewing is no more criticism than writing fiction well automatically qualifies one to write wisely about it. In the *Signal* collection, John Rowe Townsend says that, when it comes to children's literature, "there is little writing that . . . could be dignified by the name of criticism." It is sad to report that these three books do little to correct that. It is even sadder to report that, with the partial exception of the *Signal* collection, they do not particularly even try to correct it. Their editors have simply accepted the convention that what children's writers have to say about their books should interest readers of those books; they all contain numerous discussions of the creative process and little in the way of critical analysis.

Perhaps I should not be angered by that. Discussions by children's writers of how they came to write their novels are, indeed, an established genre; these three books do little that is different from many earlier books. But they do anger me. They anger me because they are so similar to those earlier books, and because they keep the focus of discussion of children's books on the creative process rather than on the results of that process. I suspect children's literature will not get the respect it deserves until it is read carefully by readers whose only bias is their pleasure in reading children's literature, without having necessarily written it first.

But many of these writers seem to believe that that sort of careful reading is dangerous. In fact, dismissive comments on criticism seem to be a significant aspect of the genre, almost *de rigueur* for writers writing about their own work. (As Eleanor Cameron's gracious response to my critical discussion of her novel *Beyond Silence* in this issue reveals, not all writers are hostile to criticism.) Even John Rowe Townsend, who is a critic as well as a writer, expresses a surprising disdain for critical analysis: "I have never greatly cared for laying works of art out on the slab and taking them to pieces; it is all too easy to finish up with nothing but dead remnants." It would also be all too easy to accuse Townsend himself of laying children's books out on the slab in his own critical writing; but despite his negative metaphor, I suspect he has done more illuminating of them than permanent damage.

If even a critic feels the need to make dismissive comments about criticism in the context of a discussion of how he writes his novels, then it should not be surprising that writers who are not critics often seem to be quite proud of their critical ineptitude. In *Celebrating Children's Books*, Arnold Lobel unashamedly announces that "in the matter of my work and children's books in general, articulate I am not." He is right; he is not articulate. I don't blame him for that; but I see no logic in the apparent assumptions of the editors of this book: first, that he could perhaps be articulate, and second, that his declaration that he isn't might be useful information. I also find little use in Lloyd Alexander's true statement in the same book that everything he says could be learned "in greater detail better expressed from any book on narrative technique"; and I am annoyed when, having admitted his own inability to describe the distinguishing qualities of good literature, Alexander says he is "not at all sure they can be defined." Many other writers share his disdain for the possibilities of critical understanding. In *The Openhearted Audience*, Pamela Travers says that the qualities of good writing "can't be described," and Ivan Southall says they are "almost impossible to define"; and in *Celebrating Children's Books*, Robert Cormier says, "Too much theorizing worries me," and Susan Cooper asks, "How can we define what we are doing? How can a fish describe what it's like to swim?"

I doubt that a fish can, or should. But I am not a fish. As an unrepentant critic and analyzer, I may even be a fisherman (although I try to keep my catches alive enough to throw them back in after I've caught them, rather than laying them out on slabs for filleting). The point is, I am a reader, not a writer of fiction. My annoyance with all these anticritical pronouncements of writers is that, consciously or not, they seem to be recommending to their readers an attitude that might well be essential to their own continuing creativity as writers but that is unnecessarily limiting for readers. We can, and should, think about the qualities of good books, even if their writers can't or don't want to.

Because many of them don't want to, what they have produced here is not often illuminating. As self-analysis, it is of special interest to the self doing it. Virginia Hamilton wonders *why* she chose to write about eccentrics; as a reader, I am more interested in *what* she writes about them, and *how* she does it. And what am I, as a reader, to do with Maurice Sendak's idea that his characters' attitudes represent his own activity "as a creative artist who also gets freer with each book and opens up more and more?" That matters to Sendak; for other readers of his books, it's just gossip.

If discussions about how books came to be written don't often throw much light on the finished books themselves, they might nevertheless offer insights into the act of writing. In fact, the frequent agreement among the writers represented in these books to a few central ideas does suggest that there is something distinct about the creative processes of those who write for children. One of those ideas is the conviction that writing is not a conscious act, that stories and characters come from somewhere below the conscious mind. Eleanor Cameron says in *The Openhearted Audience* that "there is nothing more mysterious than the ability of the unconscious to present the writer with his characters"; numerous others suggest that their books come from "the depths," or "somewhere lower down in the less accessible regions of mental experience," or "at the deepest roots of being," or "from deep sources within." Furthermore, many of them seem to equate these depths with childlike feelings. In *The Openhearted Audience*, Maurice Sendak says, "I have the mind of a child," Ivan Southall says, "I become a child," and

Eleanor Cameron makes a specific connection between childhood and the unconscious: "All the impressions of childhood are still there in the depths."

Many of these accomplished children's writers also insist that they don't write for children, neither the children they know nor children in general. Rather they write for themselves. But they almost always add the proviso that the self they write for is some aspect of the child they once were and believe they can still contact: the child of the depths.

The frequent reiteration of such ideas does say something about the distinct sort of imagination needed to write children's books. But it does something else, too. Despite the fear expressed by many of these same writers of critical analysis, it suggests how critics might come to understand the significant differences between children's books and other sorts of writing. In other words, these discussions of writers about how they write, while unilluminating in themselves, might help critics to better understand what children's writers have written.

A series of three perceptive and stimulating discussions by critics in the *Signal* collection suggests how. First, Charles Sarland does a detailed analysis of the prose of William Mayne, to show how Mayne's evocation of childhood implies a reader who is not child-like. Peter Hunt builds on Sarland's conclusion, and finally, Aidan Chambers adds to it the conception of an "implied reader," borrowed from Wolfgang Iser, in a stimulating attempt to define the audience implied by children's fiction. These three articles show what criticism of children's literature might be; the one by Chambers was the deserving recipient of the first award for critical writing given by the Children's Literature Association. But they are more than just good criticism, for the light they cast, quite unintentionally, upon the many comments of children's writers about how they write points the way to an even deeper understanding of children's literature, a literature peculiarly governed by the inevitable gulf between those who write it and the audience it implies.

If such an understanding emerges, it will be from the critical writing of readers, not from writers' discussions of how they came to write their books. That is not to say writers cannot be critics; books by

John Rowe Townsend and Eleanor Cameron show that it is possible to be good at both these different pursuits, and many of the other writers represented in these three collections express the sort of insight that can only come from much reading and much thinking about what one has read. But such insights must necessarily come only occasionally in discussions that focus on the creative process rather than on the works that result from it; and we have to acknowledge, finally, that even a writer's pronouncements about his own work come after the fact, that when writers talk about their books they are talking as readers like the rest of us, and not writers. As Alan Garner insists, "Everything I say *about* writing is with hindsight."

Garner makes that statement during an interview with Aidan Chambers, included in the *Signal* collection, an interview that sums up what it is about the attention paid to the creative process in discussions of children's books that distresses me. Garner is a fine writer, and Chambers a fine critic. But Chambers is so convinced that writers ought to have valuable things to say about their books that he badgers Garner about it, in a most unseemly fashion. After fifty pages or so, Garner finally admits to Chambers's ideas about the implied reader and such. He ought not to have had to do that. His writing speaks eloquently for itself, to sensitive readers, and Chambers's critical ideas are persuasive enough to have no need of a writer's acceptance of them. Nevertheless, Chambers did do this interview, and Garner did agree to do it; their mutual acceptance of a longstanding pattern in discussions of children's literature suggests an important reason for the relative inadequacy of the criticism of this one particular sort of writing.